

Master thesis
for the award of the academic degree Master of Science

**Developing and Evaluating Infrastructure for
ERC to Communicate with Data Repositories
and Computing Services**

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25.07.2022

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6900024](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6900024)

Abstract

Nowadays, the results of geographic research and their complexity differ greatly from those in the past. Through technical progress, researchers all over the world have the opportunity to create scientific results based on complex computations run by specially written software, often written by the researchers themselves. This leads to an enormous amount of different software and runtime environments, resulting in approximately as many unique research environments as there are researchers. To still have the opportunity to publish research reproducibly, the 'Executable Research Compendia' (ERC) was developed. An ERC can be uploaded to 'o2r' and executed on an online execution infrastructure. In current state, an ERC runs in an offline sandbox environment, without possibilities to access external services like online data repositories or geospatial computing services. This work extends the concept of ERCs to let them break out of their offline sandbox environment. To still be able to guarantee reproducibility, the access to external services must be restricted to trusted ones by the journals the ERCs are published in. Therefore, a concept was developed to restrict access to external services by applying allow lists to ERCs and assigning them to DNS servers, responsible for applying the lists.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Nowadays, the results of geographic research and their complexity differ greatly from those in the past. Through technical progress, researchers all over the world have the opportunity to create scientific results based on complex computations run by specially written software, often written by the researchers themselves. This leads to an enormous amount of different software and runtime environments, resulting in approximately as many unique research environments as there are researchers [31]. At the same time, the way of publishing scientific research has stayed the same, most research is still published in a paper based form, i.e. in text, figures and tables. The research environment and software used to produce the scientific results are usually not included.

This discrepancy between the complexity of the computations of scientific results and the simplicity of paper based publishing leads to many problems. First of all, it is crucial for the peer review process that research can be reproduced. Without reproducibility, it is not clear how the scientist got to the presented results, i.e. the research results can not be verified by the reviewer, making the research less reliable [18, 27]. Only if the the reviewer in a peer review process has access to the computational environment the results were computed in, can research be properly reviewed.

But there are more reasons research needs to be published reproducibly: One main reason is for example the possibility to re-use scientific data and results to build on existing research, making reproducibility a 'cornerstone' of science [26]. Without reproducibility, scientists need to start from scratch every time [27]. But still, most published research is not published reproducibly [26]. A survey from 2016 with 1,500 participating researchers found that over 50% could not reproduce their own research and more than 70% could not reproduce the results of other researchers [37].

There are several reasons why researchers do not provide the full reproducible environment: First of all, there are general problems in the world of science when it comes to the term 'Reproducibility'. Often, it is not clear for researchers what the term 'reproducibility' really means. The definition of reproducibility ranges from 'a detailed description of the used methods' to 'public access to data, code and methods to achieve the same results' [26]. Often, researchers provide natural language descriptions thinking it is enough to reproduce their research, but natural language descriptions 'may be converted to computer code in various ways, each of which might lead to different numerical outcomes' [21]. Secondly, there are personal reasons why researchers do not publish their research reproducibly. For example, researchers fear risking damage to their own reputation if the computations are erroneous [27, 17] or they think that it is too much work to clean the code before publishing [3]. Last, there are technical challenges when it comes to publishing reproducible research, like capturing the researchers computational

environment. Just providing access to the materials used for the computations does not necessarily lead to reproducibility, the whole computational environment is needed to guarantee reproducibility [9, 26, 21]. This work will concentrate on these technical challenges.

The 'Executable Research Compendium' (ERC) was developed to address the technical challenges in publishing reproducible research, make the sharing and reuse of computational workflows easier [31] and will serve as the basis for this work. With the ERC, a compendium based publication process has been introduced. Such a compendium includes the paper, source code, dataset and the computational environment the results were produced in. In this way it is possible to share, archive and reuse the research.

At the current state, the complete dataset and computing workflow needs to be saved inside the ERC. The ERC runs in an offline sandbox environment, so it is not possible to let an ERC 'break out' of its offline sandbox environment to communicate with external services. This is intentional so that the promise can be made that everything that was used to create the outputs is captured inside the ERC. This approach is no problem for small datasets, but for large datasets, i.e. of a size that prohibits replication for archival, this concept is not feasible, because the ERC can grow to huge containers, which makes it impractical to share and store them. Also, the large datasets used in geosciences are often remote sensing imagery, which are stored with trustworthy organisations, e.g. Sentinel Hub ¹ (developed in partnership with ESA (European Space Agency)) or the Earth Explorer ² (By the USGS (United States Geological Survey)). Other possibilities for data access are the OGC Web Service Standards (WMS ³, WFS ⁴, WCS ⁵). Furthermore, there is an increasing development of open processing infrastructures (e.g. OpenEO [36]) to be able to handle such large datasets.

As Nüst et. al. state, 'larger scale undertakings with high computational or storage requirements, e.g. distributed infrastructures, and using external third-party services [were] out of the scope' in the past [31]. This means, in the current state it is not possible to make use of data repositories or computing services inside an ERC.

1.2 Aim

As stated before, the concept of the Executable Research Compendia [31] and the architecture that has been developed [32] will serve as the basis for this work. With the Executable Research Compendium and the corresponding architecture, there is an existing infrastructure capable of capturing complete research environments, including the code, runtime environment, scientific paper and metadata to a container making the whole research reproducible.

The aim of this work is to extend the existing infrastructure to let the ERCs 'break out' of their sandbox environment to enable communication with external services, i.e. trusted data repositories and computing services.

The risk of letting an ERC communicate with external services is to lose reproducibility in the case that a data repository may not provide access to specific data in future. When making

¹<https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>

²<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>

³<https://www.ogc.org/standards/wms>

⁴<https://www.ogc.org/standards/wfs>

⁵<https://www.ogc.org/standards/wcs>

use of data repositories, it should be ensured those repositories respect the TRUST and FAIR principles [28, 42]. To achieve this, the publisher who runs the system and the journals the authors publish their Compendia in should have control over which external services are allowed to be used.

Those allow lists created by the publisher and journals then need to be applied on the corresponding ERCs. I.e., the internet access of an ERC should be restricted using the allow lists provided by the publisher and the journals so that inside ERCs only allowed external services can be used. Requests to not allowed services will then return an error, making the compendium not executable. Important here is that complex queries and resolvable URLs need to be controlled invisibly to the user. If an author is using a DOI address [35], it is not visible at first sight to which service this URL redirects (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3709390> redirects to <https://zenodo.org/record/4626854>). In a case like this, the system needs to discover to which service the DOI URL redirects in order to have full control over which services are used.

Since the ERC implementation is based on Docker ⁶, this thesis will evaluate a prototype using Docker containerisation technology and its possibilities to control network communication.

1.3 Research Questions

The aims explained above lead to the following research questions:

1. In which way is it possible to let an ERC communicate with external data repositories and (standardised) geospatial data and processing services?
2. What are the possibilities to control allowed actions (connections) performed by an ERC?
3. Can access via complex queries and resolvable URLs for data access be controlled invisibly to the user?

⁶<https://www.docker.com/>

2 Related work

2.1 Reproducibility

The importance of reproducibility in science has increased in recent years. Since every researcher has access to computers and software, the amount of unique research environments corresponds the number of researchers [31]. This leads to the problem that most research is not reproducible anymore. As a survey conducted by *Nature*¹ found out, more than half of 1500 researchers from various scientific disciplines were not able to reproduce their own or another researcher's results [2]. Kedron et. al. stated that the scientific method is predicated on the assumption that research designs and results can be reproduced, but many studies fail to reach reproducibility, whereas the field of geographic research is vulnerable to criticism because of the intricacies of geographic phenomena and spatial data analyses [24]. Moreover, without reproducibility research results cannot be verified completely in the peer review process [27]. Because of this, it is especially important to publish research reproducibly.

One reason research is not published reproducibly is that the definition of the term 'reproducibility' seems not to be clear in the scientific world. Konkol et. al. found out that the definition of 'reproducibility' ranges from the 'description of used methods' to 'public access to data, code and methods used to achieve the same results' [26]. The problem with just having a description of the methods used is that 'natural language descriptions may be converted into computer code in various ways, each of which may lead to different numerical results' and 'natural language descriptions cannot hope to avoid ambiguous program implementations' [21].

But even with full access to the used materials, including the used data and code, it is not guaranteed that research can be reproduced [9, 21]. Reproducibility often has 'consisted of tracking the provenance of the produced and published results', but this does not provide any knowledge about the research environment the results were produced in [39].

The reasons for not publishing reproducible research vary. First of all, many researchers fear damage to their reputation if published computations are erroneous [27], even if publishing reproducible, also erroneous computation, might help build a researcher's reputation for being an honest and careful researcher [29]. Another reason is that researchers overestimate the effort of publishing reproducibly, whereas it is not important how 'polished' the used code is [3]. As a third reason, the technical challenges are identified. Currently, there are no established technical solutions for capturing the entire research environment, which leads to too high a workload on the researcher's side. As Konkol et. al. found out, a lack of supporting tools are one of the biggest obstacles while publishing reproducible research [26]. By addressing these problems, the problem of a lack of reproducibility could be minimised, because in general authors support the concept of reproducibility [30].

¹<https://www.nature.com/>

2.2 Execution infrastructures

In recent years, several different execution infrastructures have been developed. A selection is presented below.

2.2.1 Binder

Binder ² is an open source, publicly available execution infrastructure first released in 2016. It is capable of creating containers to capture code and the technical environment from a repository (e.g. from GitHub ³), executing those containers and provide links to share the containers with others [22]. Readers can launch the analysis in the containers and inspect the workflow in a browser [27].

2.2.2 Galaxy

Galaxy ⁴ is a web app developed to support accessible, reproducible and transparent computational research in life sciences [13]. It enables users to develop and perform computational analysis of genomic data without programming expertise [13, 27].

2.2.3 REANA

REANA ⁵ is a reusable and reproducible research data analysis platform. The system's purpose is to facilitate code and data reuse in the field of particle physics by generalising computational practises used in this field. It 'aims to facilitate the adoption of declarative workflow systems to run data analysis processes on remote compute clouds' [43]. With REANA it is possible to run computations written in python, C and C++, furthermore it is capable of executing Jupyter Notebooks.

2.2.4 ReproZip

ReproZip ⁶ is an open source tool addressing the technical challenges of preserving and replicating research, databases, applications and software [41]. By providing a set of CLI commands, code, data and the computational environment can be encapsulated and later executed. [27]. The execution can either be conducted on a server provided by ReproZip [38] or locally.

2.2.5 o2r

o2r ⁷ originates from the geosciences and introduced a compendium based publication process using the Executable Research Compendia [31]. The developed infrastructure can be run by publishers who want to extend their infrastructure with a reproducibility service [27]. Authors can log in via ORCID [16] and publish their research including code (R Markdown), data and the paper by uploading a complete workspace. In this way it is possible to archive, reuse and

²<https://mybinder.org/>

³<https://github.com/>

⁴<https://usegalaxy.org/>

⁵<https://reana.io>

⁶<https://www.reprozip.org/>

⁷<https://o2r.uni-muenster.de/>

share the researcher’s complete research environment. Due to bindings, authors can create interactive UI elements, allowing others to change selected parameters to examine their impact on the results.

All the presented execution infrastructures have in common that the access to external services can not be controlled in any way. While Binder, Galaxy, REANA and ReProZip allow full access to external services, o2r forbids any access to ensure no forbidden services or untrustworthy data repositories are used.

2.3 Data Repositories

As stated by Brase in 2009, the lack of access to scientific data is an obstacle in international research. It leads to duplication of efforts and the verification of results becomes more difficult. With data not or only privately published by a researcher, multiple issues arise, such as poor preservation properties or the lack of data quality assessment [5]. According to Brase, data publication needs to meet two criteria: Persistence and quality.

To address the obstacle of not publicly published data, public archiving has been made mandatory by many publishers and funding agencies, whereby the usage of data repositories is preferred over supplementary materials [23, 18]. Because of this, the development of domain specific data repositories increases, and by collaborating with journals for facilitating peer reviewed data publication, the number of trusted data repositories is growing [23]. As a result, many publishers and journals provide lists of trusted data repositories in their data policies [18]. To be seen as a trusted data repository, the repository should follow the TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology) and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles [28, 42].

One possibility to meet the criteria for data publication is to make use of the DOI system [35]. In the past, URL was a broadly accepted format to address objects on the internet, but URLs can change over time, making resources no longer available. One solution is to make use of persistent identifiers, i.e. separate the identity of an object from its location on the web [25]. With DOIs, this is possible, leading to better accessibility and citability by providing users with assurance about data persistence [8].

To enable the usage of DOIs for data publication, DataCite ⁸ was founded to govern the system for assigning DOIs for research data [25].

Over the years, various data repositories have been created, both domain specific and multidisciplinary. One example for a domain specific data repository is PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science ⁹. Pangaea is defined as an ‘open access library aimed at archiving, publishing and distributing georeferenced data from earth system research’ [34]. Datasets in the PANGAEA repository are accessible via a DOI, making the data

⁸<https://datacite.org/>

⁹<https://www.pangaea.de/>

persistent. An example of a multidisciplinary data repository is Figshare ¹⁰. Figshare does not address a specific domain in the scientific world and can be used by researchers from all scientific fields. Figshare 'allows researchers to publish all of their data in a citable, searchable and sharable manner.' [34].

To create an overview about the increasing number of data repositories and their functionalities, the project re3data ¹¹ was started in 2012, indexing data repositories and providing insight about their features (e.g. data quality management, whether the repository uses DOIs, etc). With re3data, it is possible for researchers, funding organisations, libraries and publishers to get an overview of the huge amount of data repositories, helping to identify appropriate repositories [34].

2.4 Computing Services

Due to technical developments and open data policies adopted by governments and space agencies, the amount of openly available earth observation data has greatly increased. In 2019 alone, 5 petabyte of data was gathered by Landsat-7 and -8 and the first three Sentinel missions (Sentinel 1-3) [14, 40]. Because these big datasets often cannot be processed on a personal computer due to too weak hardware, there was a need for openly available infrastructures capable of handling those big datasets. This led to a development of different cloud computing systems that can be accessed via an API on the web.

One example for such a computing service is Google Earth Engine ¹², launched by Google in 2010. The Google Earth Engine 'consists of a multi-petabyte analysis-ready data catalog co-located with a high-performance, intrinsically parallel computation service', accessible via an interactive development environment (IDE) and a REST application programming interface (API) [15]. The API can be further accessed by using the Earth Engine package for javascript ¹³ or python ¹⁴. The data catalog of the Earth Engine 'is a multi-petabyte curated collection of widely used geospatial datasets [...] including the entire Landsat archive as well as complete archives of data from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, but it also includes climate forecasts, land cover data and many other environmental, geophysical and socio-economic datasets' [15]. This data can be processed by the user with more than 800 functions, 'which range in complexity from simple mathematical functions to powerful geostatistical, machine learning, and image processing operations' [15].

Another example is Sentinel Hub ¹⁵, developed by Sinergise. Sentinel Hub provides access to data and visualisation services, whereas the free version only allows viewing, selection and downloading of raw data. If a user wants to process data and make usage of OGC protocols and the REST API, the user has to choose a paid plan. [14]. In addition to remote access, Sentinel Hub provides a web interface (EO Browser) providing the possibility to investigate datasets, visualise datasets with different configurations or create new visualisations.

¹⁰<https://figshare.com>

¹¹<https://www.re3data.org/>

¹²<https://earthengine.google.com/>

¹³<https://www.npmjs.com/package/@google/earthengine>

¹⁴<https://pypi.org/project/earthengine-api/>

¹⁵<https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>

Besides these computing services, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) was developed, establishing a European data infrastructure, integrating high-capacity cloud solutions [6]. EOSC provides an overview about all kinds of services, including cloud processing services, and provides the user with details about each service and how to access the service. With EOSC, it is possible to find the best fitting service for a specific problem, leading to a better transparency regarding computing services.

Because over the years a huge amount of different processing services were developed and every service has its own capabilities, infrastructure and syntax, OpenEO ¹⁶ was developed in 2017. OpenEO provides the possibility for researchers to develop their analysis using a single standard that can be processed in multiple systems [14], eliminating the problem of the need to choose one specific service. The OpenEO API is accessible via R, python and javaScript packages, providing access to following services: CREODIAS, EODC, EURAC, Google Earth Engine, mundialis, Sentinel Hub and VITO. The user can obtain further information about the services, such as which collections they offer or which processes can be used. Finally, the user can create workflows including the choosing of datasets, processes and output format.

2.5 Docker

Docker ¹⁷ is an open source containerisation technology, capable of saving whole runtime environments in a container. The concept of Docker containers is similar to virtual machines, with the major difference that Docker containers share the kernel with the underlying host machine, leading to a much smaller size and higher performance [10, 12]. With the Docker containerisation technology, it is possible to address the problem that 'replicating the results [of existing research], extending the approach or testing the conclusions in other context, or even merely installing the software used by the original researchers can become immensely time-consuming if not impossible' by solving the 'dependency hell' with its images [4]. By having all artifacts belonging to a paper packaged and documented inside a Docker container, reproduction of research becomes possible. Other scientists are able to make use of the container 'without the need of internal knowledge and without dependency issues' [10].

Because of the advantages the Docker containerisation technology offers, reproducibility services like Binder or O2R are already using this technology [31, 22].

Since it is important to have control over the network traffic of docker containers created for reproducible research, and the user needing to rely on the network traffic not being manipulated by third party applications, network security plays a major role. Since the connectivity between docker containers and the host machine is provided using a Virtual Ethernet Bridge named *docker0* that automatically forwards packets between its network interfaces without any filtering, docker containers are vulnerable to ARP spoofing and MAC flooding attacks [7, 11]. This problem can be mitigated by using the `-icc=false` parameter, which forbids network communication between the containers. Furthermore, the Linux capabilities the container is able to use can be restricted by using the `--cap-add` or `--cap-drop` parameter, making it possible to give the container only those capabilities that are really needed [11].

¹⁶<https://openeo.org/>

¹⁷<https://docker.com>

3 Methodology

3.1 Expert interviews

In order to determine the requirements the system needs to fulfill, expert interviews were conducted. Therefore, the important stakeholder communities were defined, i.e. publishers, editors, authors, readers, reviewers and librarians [31, 27] and at least one expert of every stakeholder community was interviewed. The interviews were about 30 minutes and the interviewed experts could answer freely to openly asked questions.

To have an assessment about the interviewee’s overall attitude to reproducibility, the interviews always start with general questions about their relation to and experiences with reproducibility, i.e. if an author already has published a fully reproducible paper and why (not), whether it is important for a publisher, reviewer or editor that research is published reproducible or whether it is important for a librarian to also provide access to data, code and procedures used for scientific research.

For the analysis of the interviews and the compilation of the requirements resulting from the interviews, the interviews were recorded with the interviewees consent.

The result of these expert interviews was a requirements list including specific requirements formulated by each stakeholder community individually:

For authors it is important that the system is easy to use. If a journal has restrictions as to what services can be used, there should be easy and fast ways to find out which services these are. Moreover, it should be possible to find out which journals would accept an ERC based on the user services.

For readers it is important they can rely on the persistence of the used services. No matter how well a service pays attention to the persistence of offered data, there is always the possibility

Author	Reader	Publisher	Editor/Reviewer	Librarian
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offensively communicate allowed services • Check which journals would allow an ERC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Save data structure to ERC if data from external services used 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data repository management using re3data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Log internet usage of ERC • List used domains inside ERC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Save datacite schema for external data resources • Use re3data schema for repositories

Table 3.1: Requirements resulting from the expert interviews

Figure 3.1: o2r deployment architecture [33]

of a broken URL or data loss. Because of this, the requirement was formulated to save the structure of used data inside the ERC, so in case the original data is lost, there is the possibility to replicate the research with other data in the same structure.

For publishers it is important, just as for authors, that the system is easy to use. It was mentioned during the interviews that the allowed-service management is imagined to be very complex, which would discourage publishers from using the whole system. Since there is an existing service for metadata about data repositories, i.e. re3data¹, the requirement was formulated to integrate the functionality of re3data into the allowed-services management.

For editors and reviewers it is important to have a good overview about the used services inside an ERC. There were two requirements formulated for this: To log the whole internet usage by an ERC, or to list all domains an ERC sent requests to.

For librarians it is important to include the metadata of used data resources and repositories using the datacite² and re3data schema. By doing this it can be assured that the important information about data used for research is not lost in case of data loss.

3.2 Conceptualisation

As the first step in creating concepts, it was necessary to analyse the existing system architecture, define problems that need to be solved and find out, with which technologies the problems can be solved or circumvented.

As it can be seen in figure 3.1, the existing system consists of a nginx server handling the traffic and multiple microservices responsible for the systems functionality. The execution service, responsible for uploading workspaces, converting them to ERCs, managing, sharing and executing

¹<https://www.re3data.org/>

²<https://datacite.org/>

Figure 3.2: Concept for using a proxy server. Important: Every ERC uses the same proxy server.

ERCs is also one of these microservices. This leads to difficulties, because the nginx server and all microservices are implemented with the Docker containerisation technology using a bridge network, so there is no possibility to control the internet access at machine level. A further problem is that all ERCs are executed and managed by the same microservice. This would not lead to problems if the same list of allowed external services could be applied on all ERCs, but since the execution infrastructure is designed to be operated by a publisher publishing different journals, all of which might have different allowlists, we need to apply the correct allowlist for each ERC individually. Moreover, all ERCs are individual docker containers, which means the internet access of single containers needs to be restricted without restricting the internet access of other containers.

Based on the problems to be solved, three different approaches were defined to control requests to third party services:

1. Proxy Server:

When using a proxy server, all allowlists for the different journals would be saved inside the database and read by the proxy if needed. If a request is made by an ERC, the proxy server would parse the request and check, whether the requested service is on the corresponding journal's allowlist (figure 3.2). To make use of a proxy server is possible in Docker defining an environmental variable like `--env HTTP_PROXY="http://..."` or `--env HTTPS_PROXY="http://..."` when running a `docker build` or `docker run` command [19].

Figure 3.3: Concept for using a DNS server.

2. DNS Server:

The second approach is to make use of a Domain Name System (DNS) server. The approach is to run one DNS server for every journal individually. The allowed services for a journal would be registered inside the corresponding DNS server, so the service behind the URL registered in the DNS server would be accessible, whereas accessing not allowed services would not work, because the corresponding URL is not registered inside the DNS server, i.e. the DNS server will not know where to forward the request, leading to getting no result. (figure 3.3)

To let docker containers use a custom DNS server, the `--dns` flag can be used when running the `docker run` command. Here, the IP address of the DNS server needs to be passed.

3. IpTables:

Since the whole system is running on a Linux server, there is the possibility to make use of the IpTables firewall [1, 20] (figure 3.4). Docker adds two chains to the systems IpTable rules: `DOCKER` and `DOCKER-USER`. Dockers own rules are added to the `DOCKER` chain, while the user who runs the system has the possibility to add custom rules to the `DOCKER-USER` chain.

The idea is to create one docker network for every journal and attaching every ERC to the corresponding network when started. For each of these networks rules are defined with IpTables to allow only allowed requests coming from these networks. Since Docker

Figure 3.4: Concept for using IpTables.

assigns individual IP-addresses to every network, it is possible to restrict access to external services for each network individually.

As can be seen in the concept diagrams (figure 3.2 - 3.4), the concept of using IpTables has the advantage that both, requests and responses can be filtered. This is not possible with a DNS or proxy server.

Despite this advantage, the IpTables approach has one big problem: As can be seen in figure 3.5, the IpTables rules are defined at host network level in the *DOCKER* and *DOCKER-USER* chain, whereas the rules for journals need to be defined from inside a container already connected via a bridge network. Bridge networks are defined to be isolated from other networks, also the host network. It would be necessary to run the execution service container inside the host network to apply new rules to the *DOCKER-USER* chain. Due to this restriction with the current system architecture, the IpTables approach can not be seen as a possible solution for the problem.

Both approaches left, restricting internet access with a DNS server or with a proxy server, have in general the same architecture, even though the functionality is quite different. Inside a proxy server, the requests done by ERCs need to be parsed and checked against the allow list of the corresponding journal. To do this, the proxy server would need to access the database containing the journals information. Furthermore, there would be the need to send extra information inside a request's HTTP header to enable the proxy server to recognise to which journal the

Figure 3.5: Docker network architecture

requesting ERC belongs. The DNS server approach does not need any of this extra functionality or information. Since a DNS server is started for each journal registered and the ERCs are linked to those journal-specific DNS servers, it is not necessary to query the database for allow lists or to include journal information in the HTTP header of a request. Due to those advantages of a DNS, it was decided to fully implement the DNS server approach.

3.3 Evaluation

The evaluation of the resulting infrastructure will be divided into three different aspects: security, performance and transparency.

To evaluate the security, mocha³ integration tests will be written. The purpose is to test if the authentication functionality works properly. This is important because there should be no bug in the code allowing authors to circumvent the allowlists provided by the journals.

The performance will be tested by examining the impact of the infrastructure on the requests response time and whether the approaches have impact on the systems ability to run multiple jobs (execute multiple ERCs) at the same time. The goal is to implement an infrastructure that has no impact on the systems performance.

Finally, the transparency will be assessed against the requirements that came out of the expert interviews. As it turned out, transparency is very important to the stakeholders.

³<https://mochajs.org/>

4 Implementation

This chapter is divided into two separate sections. The first explains how the restriction to external services with a DNS server is technically achieved and which software is used. The second chapter explains how the restriction functionality is integrated into the existing system and how the management of publishers, journals and their allow lists works.

4.1 DNS server

As explained in section 3, the DNS server approach is fully implemented due to advantages over the other approaches. To be able to restrict internet access with a DNS server, first there was the need to decide which server is going to be used. It was decided to use *dnsmasq*¹, a lightweight DNS forward server for small networks. With *dnsmasq* it is possible to run a DNS server without the need of a complex configuration, making it the ideal server for the needed functionality.

The general workflow to restrict internet access based on allow lists is as following:

1. Start a *dnsmasq* server in a new Docker container
2. Apply a specific allow list on the *dnsmasq* server
3. Get the IP of the *dnsmasq* server
4. If an ERC is executed, start its container with the `--dns` flag like
`--dns=DNSSMASQ_CONTAINER_IP_ADDRESS`

The restriction is achieved by just not resolving the URLs requested by an ERC that are not allowed. An example configuration for *dnsmasq* could look like the following:

```
1 log-queries
2
3 no-hosts
4 no-resolv
5
6 cache-size=100000
7
8 server=/doi.org/8.8.8.8
9 server=/doi.pangaea.de/8.8.8.8
10 server=/openeo.org/8.8.8.8
```

This configuration is saved in a file named *dnsmasq.conf* and is automatically read by *dnsmasq* when the server is started.

The code is explained in the following:

¹<https://thekelleys.org.uk/dnsmasq/doc.html>

Line 1: All queries processed by the server are logged at system level

Line 3: Do not load the */etc/hosts* file since we do not need it.

(This file is used by *dnsmasq* to resolve computer names into IP addresses)

Line 4: Do not load the *resolv.conf* file since we do not need it.

(The content of *resolv.conf* will be inside *dnsmasq.conf*)

Line 6: Define number of allowed rules

Line 8-10: Rules for resolving URLs:

server: Indicates that a forward rule is defined

URL: If this URL is requested, the request will be forwarded

URL: Google DNS server to further process the request

Every time an ERC is started with the *--dns* flag and this ERC tries to request an external service, the request will be resolved by the specified DNS server. If the requested URL is registered inside the DNS server configuration, the request will pass through and will be further processed by the public Google DNS server. If the requested URL is not registered, it can not be resolved by the DNS server and an error will be returned. In the upper example configuration, a request to *https://doi.pangaea.de* like *https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.837248* would be forwarded to the IP 8.8.8.8, the IP address of the Google DNS server. A request to *https://zenodo.org* like *https://zenodo.org/record/57075#.YUnaiLr7SV4* would not be forwarded because the DNS server can not resolve this URL. With this functionality it is possible to restrict access to external services individually for single Docker containers by applying different allow lists.

It is also possible to specify restrictions on different domain levels. For example, the rule *server=/pangaea.de/8.8.8.8* allows requests to *https://pangaea.de* and to all subdomains, so also to *https://doi.pangaea.de*, whereas the rule *server=/doi.pangaea.de/8.8.8.8* only allows requests to this specific subdomain. This enables the possibility to allow specific services at domains without allowing the use of all services at a domain.

4.2 System integration

To integrate the functionality for restricting access to external services, the existing o2r system needs to be extended. At current state, the system is designed to be run by a publisher without distinction of different journals (one publisher often publishes multiple journals). Since each journal published by the same publisher could have different lists of allowed services, a publisher/journal management system needs to be created. The current o2r architecture looks like follows:

1. A user can upload a new ERC
2. A user can make an ERC publicly available if he is the owner of the ERC or if the user level is high enough² (Editor or Admin)

²<https://o2r.info/api/#section/User-levels>

- An ERC is not publicly available from the beginning because it first needs to be checked whether the metadata is complete and correct

3. A user can delete or edit his own ERCs or also others ERCs, if the user-level is high enough³ (Editor or Admin)

First of all, the architecture and database needs to be extended by the entity *DNS* to save the different DNS server configuration in the database. The DNS entity consists of an owner, a list of allowed domains and the IP address assigned to the Docker container running the DNS server.

For the possibility to have different allow lists for different journals, the entity *Journal* is added to the system. A journal consists of a name, a list of allowed domains, an owner, a list of compendia and compendia candidates. A user can submit an ERC to a journal, so it is listed as a candidate at this journal. The journal can then review the ERC and decide whether to accept or decline the ERC. The list of allowed domains is used to create the configuration for the DNS server that will be assigned to all ERCs that are executed and assigned to the journal. The DNS server responsible for handling requests of the corresponding ERCs is directly started when a new journal is created. Therefore, a new Docker container with the Linux Alpine image⁴ is built. The content of the Dockerfile looks like the following:

```
1 FROM alpine:edge
2 RUN apk --no-cache add dnsmasq
3 EXPOSE 53/tcp 53/udp
4 COPY dnsmasq.conf /etc/dnsmasq.conf
5 CMD ["dnsmasq", "--no-daemon"]
```

It is a simple Dockerfile just installing dnsmasq inside the container, exposing the ports needed and copying the *dnsmasq.conf* that was created by the server based on the journals allow list into the container at the correct spot. Finally the server is started. The process of how a new journal is created or updated can be seen in figure 4.1 and 4.2.

In addition to the new entity *Journal*, the entity *Publisher* is added to the system. A publisher consists of a name, a list of journals assigned to this publisher, an owner and journal candidates. A journal can submit itself to a publisher, so it will be listed as a journal candidate. If the publisher accepts the journal, it is listed under the publisher's *journals*. The publisher has the possibility to upload an own list of allowed services. The allow list of a journal that wants to submit itself to a publisher needs to be a subset of the allowlist of that publisher, so the publisher has full control over used external services on his platform. With the entity *Publisher* it is now also possible to have multiple publishers. The process of how a new publisher is created or updated can be seen in figure 4.3 and 4.4.

In order to manage the allowed services, the entity *Domains* is added to the system. A domain consists of three parts: Top level domain, secondary level domain and subdomain. This structure is used to create the correct patterns inside a *dnsmasq.conf* file. Every time a new publisher or journal is created, the domains not already existing in the database are parsed and

³<https://o2r.info/api/#section/User-levels>

⁴<https://www.alpinelinux.org/>

Figure 4.1: Sequence diagram for creating a new journal

HTTP PUT /api/v1/journal/:id/update

Figure 4.2: Sequence diagram for updating a journal

Figure 4.3: Sequence diagram for creating a new publisher

HTTP PUT /api/v1/publisher/:id/update

Figure 4.4: Sequence diagram for updating a publisher

Figure 4.5: Sequence diagram for adding a domain to a publisher

divided into the three parts and saved inside the database. The process of how a domain is added to or removed from a journal can be seen in figure 4.5 and 4.6.

The resulting database structure for this extension of the system can be seen in figure 4.7

In addition to the management of publishers, journals and allow lists, it was requested to integrate *re3data*⁵ functionality into the system. Therefore, three methods are provided to the user:

1. /api/v1/repository: List all repositories registered at *re3data*. Can be combined with a filter for a more specific search (See figure A.12)
2. /api/v1/repository/filter: Returns a JSON with all possible filters that can be applied
3. /api/v1/repository/:id: Get a specific repository by ID (See figure A.13)

In the following, all new functionality is listed and explained:

⁵<https://www.re3data.org/>

- Publisher
 - HTTP POST `/api/v1/publisher`: Create a new publisher (figure 4.3)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/publisher`: List all publishers (figure A.15)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/publisher/:id`: Get full information about publisher by ID (figure A.9)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/publisher/:id/view`: Get public information about publisher (figure by ID A.20)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/publisher/:id/domains`: Get a publishers allowed services by ID (figure A.10)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/publisher/:id/journals`: Get all journals assigned to a publisher by ID (figure A.11)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/publisher/:id/update`: Update a publisher by ID (figure 4.4)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/publisher/:id/adddomain`: Add a domain to a publisher’s allow list (figure A.3)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/publisher/:id/removdomain`: Remove a domain from a publisher’s allow list (figure A.17)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/publisher/:id/addjournal`: Add a journal to a publisher (figure A.5)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/publisher/:id/confirmjournal`: Accept a journal candidate for a publisher (figure A.6)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/publisher/:id/removejournal`: Remove a journal from a publisher (figure A.18)

- Journal
 - HTTP POST `/api/v1/journal`: Create a new journal (figure 4.1)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/journal`: List all journals (figure A.14)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/journal/possiblejournals`: Get all journals that would accept an ERC based on the used external services (figure A.16)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/journal/:id`: Get full information about a journal (figure A.8)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/journal/:id/view`: Get public information about a journal (figure A.19)
 - HTTP GET `/api/v1/journal/:id/domains`: Get a journals allowed services (figure A.7)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/journal/:id/update`: Update a journal (figure 4.2)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/journal/:id/adddomain`: Add a domain to the journal’s allow list (figure 4.5)
 - HTTP PUT `/api/v1/journal/:id/removdomain`: Remove a domain from the journal’s allow list (figure 4.6)

- HTTP PUT /api/v1/journal/:id/addtopublisher: Submit the journal to a publisher (figure A.4)
- HTTP PUT /api/v1/journal/:id/acceptcompendium: Accept a submitted compendium (figure A.1)
- Compendium
 - HTTP PUT /api/v1/compendium/:id/journal: Submit a compendium to a journal (figure A.2)

Figure 4.6: Sequence diagram for removing a domain from a publisher

Figure 4.7: Entity relationship diagram for system extension

5 Evaluation

In order to evaluate the implemented approach, it is tested for its security, transparency and performance.

5.1 Security

For security aspects, it is especially important that an author or reader has no possibility to bypass the restriction on external services of journals. Therefore it must be ensured that only users with a user level high enough for the corresponding action are allowed to perform this action. Furthermore, only users who are the owners of a journal or publisher are able to modify this journal or publisher. Finally it must be ensured that, when an ERC is executed, the restrictions to external services is always correctly applied on the ERC.

To test the aspects of creating and modifying publishers and journals, the node package mocha¹ is used. Several tests were written to ensure the server always responds with the correct HTTP code and performs the correct action. The results of the mocha tests can be seen in table 5.1. As it can be seen in the table, the system passes all tests, which ensures the authentication methods are working.

To verify that restrictions to external services are correctly applied on the executed ERCs, tests with five different configurations are performed:

- ERC not using external services
- ERC not using external services and assigned to journal
- ERC using external services, but not assigned to a journal
- ERC using external services, assigned to journal using not allowed services
- ERC using external services, assigned to journal using only allowed services

The results for these tests can be seen in table 5.2. As it can be seen in the table, the system also passed all ERC-execution tests. With this results it is ensured that the restrictions of external services are applied correctly on ERCs in every possible situation.

5.2 Transparency

To evaluate whether the required transparency has been achieved, the system is checked against the requirements formulated from the expert interviews 3.1.

For authors it is important to have a quick and easy overview about allowed services. Moreover it was asked for a method to check, which journal would accept an ERC based on the used

¹<https://mochajs.org/>

Test	Expected result	Passed
Create new publisher as Admin	should return HTTP 200	✓
as Admin	should return HTTP 400 with missing domains parameter	✓
as Admin	should return HTTP 400 with missing name parameter	✓
as Editor	should return HTTP 401	✓
as known user	should return HTTP 401	✓
as user	should return HTTP 401	✓
Add domain to publisher as Admin	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓
Remove domain from publisher as Admin and owner	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓
Add journal to publisher as Admin and owner	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓
Remove journal from publisher as Admin and owner	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓
Create new journal as Admin	should return HTTP 200	✓
as Admin	should return HTTP 400 with missing domains parameter	✓
as Admin	should return HTTP 400 with missing name parameter	✓
as Editor	should return HTTP 200	✓
as known user	should return HTTP 401	✓
as user	should return HTTP 401	✓
Add domain to journal as Admin or Editor and owner	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓
Remove domain from journal as Admin or Editor and owner	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓
Add journal to publisher as Admin or Editor and owner	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓
Accept compendium for journal as Admin or Editor and owner	should return HTTP 200	✓
as unauthorised user	should return HTTP 401 or 403	✓

Table 5.1: Results of the performed mocha tests

Use external service	Assigned to journal	Allowed services	Expected result (success / fail)	Passed
×	×	-	success	✓
×	✓	-	success	✓
✓	×	-	fail	✓
✓	✓	×	fail	✓
✓	✓	✓	success	✓

Table 5.2: Results of the performed ERC tests

services. For this purpose, two HTTP GET requests were implemented: 1) It is possible to get the allowed services of a journal by passing the journal ID (see figure A.7). 2) It is possible to get a list of journals by passing a list of service-domains. The list is checked against the allowlist of each journal and a list of journals is returned.

Editors and reviewers formulated two different ways regarding the transparency of used services inside an ERC: To log the internet traffic of an ERC and to list used domains by analysing the ERC. Since analysing the content of an ERC and filtering out all domains that are called is not possible in the current system, it was decided to log the ERCs internet traffic. This is directly done by dnsmasq, creating log files at system level.

5.3 Stakeholder requirements

In the following, it will be checked whether the requirements formulated from the expert interviews that are not related to the transparency of the system are met.

For readers it is important to have the data structure of used data inside the ERC. If an ERC pulls the data used in it from an external data repository, it might be that in future the dataset is no longer available. To still be able to replicate the research performed in the ERC, the data structure should be saved inside the ERC. In this way it is always possible to create dummy-data in case the original data is lost. Due to the fact that datasets are usually loaded with a HTTPS connection, it is not possible to load the data structure automatically, because the full URL used to get the dataset can not be parsed at runtime.

For publishers and Librarians it is important to use the re3data schema and API for the repository management. This requirement is met by including the re3data API into the system. The user is able to get lists of available repositories and to apply filters to these lists. Moreover it is possible to get full information about single repositories by passing the corresponding repository ID.

For librarians it is also important to save the datacite schema of external data resources. To achieve this, the system would need to be able to read the content of HTTPS requests, which is not possible in the current state. Therefore this requirement could not be met.

5.4 Performance

By evaluating the performance, two different aspects are considered: The impact on the response time for requests to external services and the impact on the system's ability to perform multiple

Figure 5.1: Comparison of response times with and without using a DNS server

ERC executions at the same time.

To test the impact on the response time, a script was written that performs one ERC execution every 3 seconds, 100 times. The script was executed twice: Once running an ERC connected to a DNS server and once running an ERC not connected to a DNS server. The time difference between sending the request and receiving the response was measured for every execution, leading to 100 data points for with using a DNS server and 100 for without using a DNS server. The result can be seen in figure 5.1. As it can be seen in the figure, the DNS server had no impact on the response time. The mean response time when using a DNS server was 0.3025055 seconds with a standard deviation of 0.0445795 and 0.3107337 seconds with a standard deviation of 0.04462305 when not using a DNS server.

In addition, the approach has no impact on the system's ability to execute multiple ERCs at the same time. Since the DNS server has no impact on the response time and it is able to handle multiple requests at once, the ERCs are executed with the same performance as before inserting the DNS server functionality.

6 Discussion

In the course of this work, the o2r system was extended by a component allowing the user to let ERCs break out of their offline sandbox environment and let them communicate with external online services, i.e. external data repositories and computing services. In the following, the general problems of implementing the restriction functionality and the limitations of the implemented approach will be discussed.

6.1 General problems

In this section, the general problems in implementing the restriction functionality will be discussed.

One major problem is the encryption of HTTPS requests. When a HTTPS request is made from inside an R script or R markdown file running in a docker container, it is not possible to parse the request and recognise the complete URL requested, but only the requested host. This means that if request is made to an URL like *https://zenodo.org/record/XXXXXXXX#.XXXXXXXXXXXX*, it is only recognised that a request was made to *zenodo.org*, but it is not possible to recognise the exact dataset. This results in the following restrictions:

- It is not possible to allow specific datasets or specific services provided by hosts. Either one allows requests to a host or not, there is no possibility to allow just specific queries to a host.
- In general, it is expected that journals allow requests to DOI addresses. In this case, it is not possible to restrict access to services to which the DOI address forwards the request. For example, a request to *https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.807580* is forwarded to *https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.807580*. In this case, if requests to DOI addresses are allowed by a journal but requests to *doi.pangaea.de* are not, the request will go through anyway, because it can not be recognised that the request targets to *doi.pangaea.de*. It is only recognised that the request targets *doi.org*.

These restrictions apply to DNS servers and to proxy servers. With a DNS server, it is only possible to resolve host names, i.e. a DNS server only handles the top, secondary level and sub domain.

The same applies for HTTP proxy servers. With the proxy server approach presented in the methodology chapter, a proxy server would be running without a public domain. The proxy server would only have been visible from inside the system, which means that no SSL certificate could have been applied to that proxy server, making the connection to this proxy server insecure. Consequently, the proxy server is not able to parse requests made by the ERCs, again, it is only possible to recognise the host a request is sent to.

One possibility to bypass this restriction would have been to use a firewall like IpTables. With IpTables it is possible to monitor outgoing and incoming connections, i.e. it is possible to recognise the host to which the request is sent and the host from which the response was sent. In general it appears sensible to make use of IpTables, since Docker is using the IpTables firewall itself on Linux based systems and it offers its own chain inside IpTables for custom rules for individual Docker networks. By assigning one Docker network to each journal and running all ERCs of a journal inside its network, it would have been possible to restrict the internet access for each journal individually without the need of parsing requests, just by applying the restriction rules on incoming and outgoing connections. This would not prevent ERCs from requesting not allowed services through DOI addresses, but it can be prevented that forbidden services can send responses to ERCs, which would have the same effect.

To make use of the IpTables firewall is currently not possible in the existing system architecture, because the rules need to be applied from inside a Docker container running in a bridge network, i.e. it is not possible to modify the IpTable rules from this container, because it does not have access to the network configuration at machine level.

Finally, there is the problem that first parsing request URLs and checking then against allow lists can have an impact on the systems performance, i.e. enlarging response times of requests or preventing the system from running multiple ERCs at once. This is especially a problem when using a proxy server if too many ERCs are making requests at once which might lead to exceeding the proxy's processing power. By using a DNS server or the IpTables firewall, this problem can be bypassed since these technologies not have such an impact on the system's performance.

6.2 Result's limitations

As already discussed in the previous section, one big limitation of the DNS server approach is that only outgoing requests can be monitored based on the requested host. When using a DNS server, this problem can not be solved since a DNS server is always a forward server, i.e. it takes requests and resolves the host's IP address the request should be forwarded to. Monitoring incoming connection, i.e. the responses sent by external services, is not possible with a DNS server. This results in a loss of control for journals, since one has to decide whether DOI addresses should be accessible or not. If yes, every dataset assigned to a DOI address can be loaded inside an ERC, independent which data repository actually provides access to the dataset. On the other hand, journals probably do not want to forbid accessing datasets with DOI addresses since using the DOI system for data publication is on the rise and it is very important to make datasets persistent [25]. To forbid access to DOI addresses would basically be a step backwards in motivating researchers to publish their datasets and enlarging the value of openly available research data.

Another limitation of the implemented approach is that not all requirements can be met. It was requested by authors and librarians to save the data structure of used external datasets saved inside the ERC in order to have the possibility to recreate data in case the original dataset is lost or the URL is broken. It was requested by authors to save the data structure, librarians asked for saving the datacite schema for external resources. Both requirements could not be

met due to the problem of not being able to fully parse HTTPS requests, i.e. not being able to recognise which dataset exactly was requested. This prevents the system from being able to automatically save the data structure inside the ERC. A possible future solution for this could be to make it mandatory to upload the datacite scheme, if an external dataset is used, to the ERC when uploading it. Therefore it must be recognised if an external dataset is used automatically, which is beyond the scope of this work.

Besides this, the implemented approach allows users to also load sensitive data, which results in both advantages and disadvantages in using ERCs. One advantage is that, when data is loaded on runtime inside the ERC, it is not stored permanently in the ERC or on the system, making it safe to run an ERC with sensitive data on the o2r execution infrastructure. The disadvantage here is that at the current state of the system there is no possibility to restrict access to specific ERCs and making them only executable for specific users. This would be crucial, since it should be prevented that sensitive data could be accessed by any user.

Furthermore, many data repositories and computing services require authentication when accessing their services. This authentication is usually done by sending user credentials, either as a HTTP header or directly written in the URL, which happens inside the R code of an ERC. This is a problem since users can not manipulate the R code of an ERC, i.e. it is not possible for users to authenticate a service when running an ERC that requires authentication information to load data or to perform processing at online processing services. Since authors should not upload an ERC with their personal user credentials inside the code, it must be ensured in future that input fields are provided to users for user credentials if an ERC is executed that communicates with services that require authentication.

7 Conclusion

This research explored different approaches to restricting access to external services like online data repositories and computing services for ERCs based on allow lists created by the journals the ERCs are published in. It was shown that it is possible to apply the restriction with different technologies, with one approach fully implemented. At the beginning of this work, three research questions were formulated which can now be answered.

In the first research question it was asked in which way it is possible to let an ERC communicate with external data repositories and (standardised) geospatial data and processing services. By changing the configuration the containers containing the ERCs are started with, it is possible to let the ERCs break out of their offline sandbox environment and allow requests to those services, resulting in the possibility to load external datasets inside the ERC and process data with geospatial computing services.

For the second research question, three different approaches were presented that all provide functionality to control allowed actions (connections) performed by an ERC. It was shown that using IpTables would have been the best solution, since Docker uses this firewall for its network isolation functionality and offers an extra chain where restriction functionality can be implemented. Furthermore, with IpTables incoming and outgoing connections can be restricted. In the end, the DNS server approach was implemented because the current system architecture prevents the use of IpTables. By defining allow lists for journals, it is possible to create DNS server configurations ensuring only allowed actions can be performed by an ERC, with the limitation that the allow lists can only be applied on requests, not on responses, resulting in a loss of control for journals if the response is sent from a different host than the request was sent to.

The third research question asked whether it is possible to control access via complex queries and resolvable URLs invisibly to the user. Here it must be said that this is not possible with the presented approaches. Since requests are performed via HTTPS connections, only the host requested can be recognised, but there is no possibility to recognise the full URL with which a request was performed, which is basically the purpose of HTTPS requests.

In the end, a system was developed with which it is possible to apply journal's allow lists to requests performed by an ERC. Journals can manage their allow lists by using the re3data API and have always the full control over which services can be requested by ERCs published in their journals. It is now possible to load data from online data repositories inside an ERC and to perform complex processing on the data by using geospatial processing services.

8 Future work

For future work, one big issue is the authentication process when sensitive data is requested by an ERC. When sensitive data is requested, it must be ensured that only users that are allowed to access this data can request it successfully. This can either be done by having input fields for user credentials or by connecting the user accounts on the o2r infrastructure with other accounts at online data repositories.

Moreover, in future the system architecture could be restructured so that the use of IpTables would be enabled, which would lead to a much better control over which actions can be performed by ERCs, because then not only the requests made by ERCs can be monitored but also the responses to those requests, so when requests to DOI addresses are allowed, the journal does not lose control over which services are requested with those DOI addresses.

Finally it can be tested whether the proposed approaches also work on other infrastructures than the o2r infrastructure, e.g. with the Binder infrastructure [22].

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A Appendix

HTTP PUT /api/v1/journal/:id/acceptcompendium

Figure A.1: Accept compendium for journal

HTTP PUT /api/v1/compendium/:id/journal

Figure A.2: Submit compendium at journal

HTTP PUT /api/v1/publisher/:id/adddomain

Figure A.3: Add a domain to a publisher

Figure A.4: Submit a journal at a publisher

HTTP PUT /api/v1/publisher/:id/addjournal

Figure A.5: Add a journal to a publisher

HTTP PUT /api/v1/publisher/:id/confirmjournal

Figure A.6: Confirm a journal candidate for a publisher

HTTP GET /api/v1/journal/:id/domains

Figure A.7: Get allowed domains at journal

HTTP GET /api/v1/journal/:id

Figure A.8: Get a journal

HTTP GET /api/v1/publisher/:id

Figure A.9: Get a publisher

HTTP GET /api/v1/publisher/:id/domains

Figure A.10: Get all domains allowed for a publisher

HTTP GET /api/v1/publisher/:id/journals

Figure A.11: Get all journals registered at a publisher

HTTP GET /api/v1/repository

Figure A.12: Get all data repositories from re3data

HTTP GET /api/v1/repository/:id

Figure A.13: Get a repository from re3data

HTTP GET /api/v1/journal

Figure A.14: List all journals

HTTP GET /api/v1/publisher

Figure A.15: List all publishers

HTTP GET /api/v1/journal/possiblejournals

Figure A.16: Get all journals that would allow a specific domain list

HTTP PUT /api/v1/publisher/:id/removedomain

Figure A.17: Remove a domain from a publisher

Figure A.18: Remove a journal from a publisher

HTTP GET /api/v1/journal/:id/view

Figure A.19: View a journal

HTTP GET /api/v1/publisher/:id/view

Figure A.20: View a publisher